

NON-TRADITIONAL EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM AND THEIR POSSIBILITIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

*The era of glut affects all areas of life, including changes in traditional educational processes. The article deals with the problem of innovations and trends in the development of the educational environment. The modern education system is experiencing a serious crisis, which is associated with the transition from the **traditional to the nontraditional paradigm of education**. The changes that have taken place in society and the economy have required a restructuring of ideas in the field of designing the education system. Everything is moving towards a personalized approach. Due to immersion in large amounts of information and knowledge every day, attention is unfocused. Due to these changes, the demand for modern information and communication technologies is increasing day by day. In particular, the demand for these technologies is growing in the process of **non-traditional education system** (in our case teaching foreign languages as a second language), and the interest of the humanity to information and communication technologies in the education system is increasing. In the period of intensive development of information technology, especially computer, the relevance of this topic is the importance of a computer, E-mail, Internet in teaching Business English. The author analyzes the key pedagogical innovations and trends that will play a crucial role in the construction of the nontraditional education system. Among them: massive open online courses that promote networking. At the same time, the ability to think critically and learn to analyze everything will become more important than ever. Especially in case of our listeners who are from different business spheres and are interested about the situation all over the world*

connected to their business. An expert author of an online course, a methodologist, a teacher at school or a lecturer at a university will become a curator who will help you choose the right knowledge in an era of information overload. The role of the teacher will still be great: in particular, he helps to meaningfully choose those sources that need to be studied and build an educational trajectory in such a way as to systematize knowledge.

Everyone knows the importance of information technology to the development of civilization. Therefore, it is important to take into account the high technologies that come into our modern life. Information technology plays a big role. However, if you're not in the field of information technology yourself, you might not know just how information technology touches your life.

Thanks to computer technologies that provide with enormous speed the transfer of vast amounts of information from one point of the globe to any other, today's civilized humanity is entering a new, information age. The Information Age, also called the Computer Age, the Digital Age and the New Media Age, is coupled tightly with the advent of [personal computers](#). And today it is hardly possible to find a topic that is more fashionable and widely discussed than the current global information revolution and the changes to which it led and will lead in the future both in society as a whole and for each person in particular. And these changes are entering educational sphere day by day which makes it more developed and improved. It is clear that yesterday's innovation has become today's **obstacle** to change [11]. Proceeding from this, it is natural that there are no indifferent to these changes. Some of them praise and announce the beginning and the main content of the new

era in the history of mankind, the approval of the information society. Others treat them with caution, noting that these changes complicate a person's life and lead people into a virtual world that is far from reality. Still others recognize both the new opportunities and perspectives that information technologies offer, and the dangers that need to be realized and warned in time [8].

Professional development is a very important part of this **information age**. The number of students involved in studying as well as their demands is growing day by day. Meanwhile, student demographics have changed, and the definitions and differences between traditional and non-traditional students have become fuzzy. Most students today have many commitments, and they must strive for success both in training and at work. Consequently, an increasing number of students enroll in online education to receive their degrees or diplomas. In turn, higher education is increasingly stimulated by technology to meet the needs of students. Learning environments that function independently of time and place, such as those created using **computer-based communications**, satisfy these needs, giving students the flexibility and convenience of participating in classes from any place at any time. [5, 7]

Modern education has created the problem of information overload of students and the problem of orientation in an excessive amount of information.

How to be? What to do if an overloaded society simply misses some of the information especially in the sphere of education? Society put **traditional textbooks** aside and are simply absorbed in the technology by which they receive information and which leads them to **information overload**. [12]

The contradiction between the rapid rate of increase in knowledge in the modern world and the limited possibilities for their assimilation by the individual forces modern pedagogy to abandon the all-round development of the personality and move on to the development of a person's abilities for self-regulation and self-education. Modernization of education will help to overcome the crisis. The modernization of education is impossible without the introduction of information and communication technologies into the educational process. The effectiveness of computers and information technologies depends on how we use them, on the ways and forms of application of these technologies. [4]

And of course, questions arise that require an answer: what is the essence of the modern information revolution that has taken place, and what new does it bring into the life of society? What new opportunities and perspectives are opened by information technologies in all their diversity and rapid change? And how to harmonize the needs and abilities of a person with a stormy, multi-layered, rapidly growing and changing flow of information?

However, we must remember that the modern information revolution is not the first in the history of mankind.

The first and most significant information revolution that separated a person from the rest of the animal world is the emergence of oral speech, ways to formulate your thought in sound symbols and communicate it to another member of your community. A powerful channel for the accumulation and transmission of information, enrichment of knowledge and experience, and warning of dangers has emerged. This radically changed the living conditions and development of our very distant ancestors, became the foundation of their progress in prehistoric times. [2;11]

Oral speech, along with the unique ability to reflect the thoughts of a person, has several disadvantages. The most important of these shortcomings were the limitedness of the oral speech in space and in time. With the advent of writing - the second information revolution, which happened after the Neolithic revolution and to some extent was its result - these restrictions on oral speech were lifted. Humanity was able to not only transmit thoughts at a distance, but also in time [2; 1].

Over time, the growing flow of new knowledge and skills demanded new ways of consolidating and transferring the accumulated information from generation to generation, which oral speech could no longer cope with. The main features of writing include the following: unlimited in space and time; text written on paper can be reproduced anytime and anywhere; the knowledge presented is of a syntagmatic nature; the amount of text is measured by the number of pages; feedback from the delivery of the text cannot be achieved

during the delivery of the text or at the end of this - for this, a meeting with the lecturer is required; the dimensions of the text are set. [9]

The invention of symbolic information and its fixation in stone, clay tablets, on papyrus, and then on paper, multiplied many times the possibilities to accumulate, transmit and perceive knowledge and experience, information about the most important events. A new stage in the social division of labor was the emergence of groups of people professionally engaged in informational activities - scribes, readers, teachers, etc.

The third information revolution can be considered as the invention of printing. The development of sciences stimulated by book printing accelerated the rate of accumulation of knowledge systematized by branches. This knowledge could be quickly replicated, and it became available to many, often far from each other geographically and in time, participants in the intra-industry process. It was a huge step in intellectual progress, education, assimilation and transmission of scientific and cultural achievements.

The fourth information revolution can be attributed to the invention and distribution of radio and television. This made it possible to reduce distances, transmit, overcoming boundaries, the necessary information in sound or figurative form, create a growing information field covering the entire globe. A person became a citizen of the world, learning about events from any part of the world planet in real time. But again, there is no contact between a lecturer and a student.

But we must remember that electronic educational resources do not

replace a textbook. The book is a universal, fairly simple and operational means of describing objects, processes and abstractions. The medium of abstractions can only be text, which itself is a combination of symbolic abstractions. In addition, the book does not require additional technical means of reproduction, it is convenient to use anywhere and at any time.

Now we are facing a new big invention in the sphere of information technologies, a new means of communication different from both oral and written speech – computer, E –mail, internet Thanks to computer technologies that provide with enormous speed the transfer of vast amounts of information from one point of the globe to any other, today's civilized humanity is entering a new, information age The process of society informatization originates in the 60s of the last century. And today it is hardly possible to find a topic more fashionable and widely discussed than the modern global information revolution and the changes that it has led and will lead in the future, both in society as a whole and for each person in particular [8, pp. 256–266; 10]. As a result of analyzes of various texts created with the help of writing and printing, we came to the conclusion that the text displayed on a computer monitor is not a written or oral means of communication, but a means that includes the possibilities of both written and oral speech. And if with the advent of writing (and even more so, book printing) mankind in a very short time reached heights that it could not achieve in hundreds, thousands of years of its development, then the rapid development of computer technologies,

and in this regard, the invention of a new means of displaying information deserves no less attention from philology and linguistics, which this area of knowledge has been given throughout its history to written texts in their relationship with oral speech. As a result of our analyses of traditional and nontraditional textbooks we can come to a conclusion that the future of the education, especially when concerning the importance of computer technologies, nontraditional textbooks allow us to work independently wherever you are. But still we should not forget that the role of the teacher will be great: in particular, he helps to meaningfully choose those sources that need to be studied and

build an educational trajectory in such a way as to systematize knowledge.

As a result, if we take the last years, that is, the period of the pandemic, it was a great way to experience nontraditional textbooks. In the example of our listeners who are from different business spheres, those textbooks allowed us to create independent work. By creating non-traditional textbooks, as well as closely linking them to the Internet sources, our listeners, in addition to learning the language, were able to achieve two-way results: studying the Business English and situations concerning the problems and innovations in their spheres.

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